
THE SIGNIFICANCE OF ORAL SPEECH IN THE PROCESS OF LEARNING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses some features of the use of oral speech in teaching foreign languages in higher education. A brief analysis is given about the difference between the process of teaching foreign languages from other disciplines, which is characterized by dressing up direct knowledge about reality, as well as in expressing thoughts about objective reality. It also indicates important factors that a teacher should pay attention to when using oral speech as the means of teaching a foreign language.

Keywords: *oral speech, communication, learning, speaking, audio materials, speech skills.*

In connection with the progressive development of the globalization of the society, which contributes to the development and improvement of the quality of life of both ordinary people and entire states, in recent years in our country, as well as throughout the world, there has been an increasing interest in learning foreign languages. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-5117 dated May 19, 2021 “On measures to raise to a qualitatively new level activities to promote the study of foreign languages in the Republic of Uzbekistan” is a vivid example of our government paying attention to teaching the younger generation foreign languages. The purpose of the adoption of this legal act is to develop teaching foreign languages as a priority direction of educational policy, to radically improve the quality of education in this direction, to attract qualified teachers to the sphere and to increase the population's interest in learning foreign languages. Also, in order to bring the popularization of the teaching of foreign languages in our country to a new level and organize systematic work to develop the sphere, comprehensively educate the younger generation, and create all the conditions for this, the Cabinet of Ministers of

the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted Resolution No. 34 dated January 19, 2022. “On additional measures to improve the study of foreign languages”.

One of the most widely spoken languages today is English. Knowledge of the English language and fluency in it allows you to expand your horizons in any direction of scientific activity and increase intelligence. It helps scientists and researchers to make new discoveries, and entrepreneurs to develop their business. We can say that English opens the way to knowledge, business, politics, education and development. Learning English opens the door to the world library of knowledge, as many scientific and literary publications are written in English. In other words, we can say that English penetrates into all areas of our lives. Knowledge of a foreign language is very important for a comfortable life in the modern world. Taking into account the above, in our country, when preparing highly qualified personnel in the higher education system, special attention is paid to teaching foreign languages.

It should be noted that teaching foreign languages is very different from other subjects. Speaking about the difficulties of teaching a foreign language, it is impossible not to consider the concept of language. I.A. Zimnyaya offers the following definition of language: language is “a complex systemic level formation through which a person’s conceptual (verbal) thinking is formed and the development of all his higher mental functions is mediated and which is the main means of human communication.” According to W. Humboldt, language is “the soul of a nation, it captures all of its “national” character. Being a socio-historical product, language thus also provides a link between different generations that speak this language. Language is the liveliest, most abundant and strong bond that connects the obsolete, living and future generations of the people into one great, historical living whole.

Unlike other subjects, a foreign language does not give a person direct knowledge about reality, but is the means of formation and then a form of existence and expression of thoughts about objective reality, properties, the laws of which are the subject of other disciplines. Another feature of a foreign language is the specific ratio of knowledge and skills [1]. So, a foreign language in the process of mastering it involves the same big process as the "practical" disciplines, the process of forming speech skills.

Oral speech is widely used in the modern methodology of teaching foreign languages, which allows students to get involved in verbal communication. In communication, the communicative abilities of students are formed and developed, including the ability to make contact with strangers, seek their disposition and mutual

understanding, and achieve their goals. With the purposeful use of communication, there is an active process of developing those practical skills that may be needed in the future to improve professional abilities. Today, one of the main tasks of oral speech is teaching the design of messages. If the time spent on the formulation of the statement does not exceed the time spent on its pronunciation, then this largely determines the quality of the speech skill. Oral speech as the goal of learning acts as the means of communication, with the help of which information is obtained during listening, information is transmitted during utterance, information is exchanged during conversation, when oral speech is associated with the method of application in teaching a foreign language. The correct use of oral speech in the process of teaching a foreign language arouses great interest and desire among students to study it.

Oral speech, in turn, has the following important functions: motivational, which is considered as the goal of language learning, provides the opportunity for direct communication, mastering oral speech helps to overcome problems associated with self-doubt when learning a language); developing, which contributes to mastering the structure of the language in oral speech and improving other aspects of speech activity, i.e. students are provided with the opportunity to hear and see how, in what situations, the input words or grammatical structures are used [2].

It should be noted that oral speech can be presented in dialogic and monologic forms. Dialogic speech is a process of direct communication, which is characterized by alternately replacing each other and generating one another replicas of two or more persons. The main difficulty in understanding dialogic speech is that in the course of dialogic speech there is a need to follow the train of thought of the interlocutor. In this case, dialogic speech is closely related to the development of listening skills. Monologue speech is the speech of one person expressing his thoughts, intentions, and assessment of events in a more or less detailed form. Monologue speech is characterized by greater arbitrariness, consistency, harmony than dialogic [3]. The main difficulty of monologue speech is to maintain consistency, coherence, continuity, semantic completeness of the statement in the process of speaking.

In methodological terms, it is essential that listening and speaking, being in close relationship, contribute to the development of each other in the learning process. Listening is the process of listening to foreign speech, using special tests to check the level of listening comprehension. The observations of psychologists have established that the understanding of oral speech occurs as a result of the perception of speech

and its comprehension. Speaking is a type of speech activity through which oral verbal communication is carried out. Speaking can have varying complexity, ranging from expressing an effective state, naming an object, answering a question, and ending with an independent detailed statement. The main difference between these two processes is their final links - the generation of an utterance for speaking and the perception of speech for listening.

“In order to learn to understand speech, it is necessary to speak, and by how your speech will be received, judge your understanding. Understanding is formed in the process of speaking, and speaking in the process of understanding” [3]. According to A.A. Leontiev [4], inner speech and related articulation are the main mechanism of speech thinking and take place both in listening to foreign speech and in speaking. In the process of speaking, there is a preliminary fixation of thoughts with the help of inner speech, i.e. drawing up a mental plan or outline of a future statement. “Even with the direct communication of one’s thoughts at the moment of their occurrence, nevertheless, their expression in external speech is preceded by the appearance of motor speech impulses, which in all cases, at least for a fraction of a second, forestall the pronunciation of words” [3]. Both processes are accompanied by active mental activity.

Speaking is one of the main types of speech activity, which has a number of characteristics that are of direct importance to a person. It is a way of expressing thoughts by means of language. The main problem in teaching speaking is that initially there is a problem in the design of an oral message due to the fact that it is an intermediate stage between thought and the oral message itself. For its development, it is necessary to improve the corresponding speech skills. Speaking is characterized by an initiative type of speech activity, since it is aimed at meeting human needs. Speech activity, like any other type of activity, is the result of the mental, psychophysiological activity of the human brain.

Speech activity is realized due to the complex psychophysiological mechanism of speech activity. Many researchers pay attention to the connection between the psychological content of activity and the psychophysiological mechanisms of activity. In particular, in his article “On the triple aspect of the linguistic sign” L.V. Shcherba, considering the nature of the language, writes that: “The mechanism, this is the speech (activity) organization of a person, cannot in any way be equal to the sum of speech experience (this implies both speaking and understanding of a given

individual ...) a person's speech organization can only be physiological or psychophysiological”.

Determining the psychological content of speech activity, A.N. Leontiev notes that speech activity:

- is a kind of human activity and occupies a central place in the process of his psychological development;

- being included in other human activities, it performs a communicative function (a word is the particle of communication), an indicative function (a word is the way of pointing to an object), an intellectual and significative function (a word is a carrier of a generalization, a concept);

- is not a process of quantitative changes, expressed in an increase in the vocabulary and associative links of the word, but a process of qualitative changes, a process of development;

- is the unity of form and content;

- has its expression in the form of a word, which is correlated with the subject of expression (thought).

Based on the theory of A.N. Leontiev, thought as an object of speech activity in many respects "shapes the whole character of activity" [5].

Students observe a new phenomenon in oral speech, listen in order to understand the meaning of the material being introduced. The attention of students is directed to the content of the statement, in which new information is presented. Their task is to understand, comprehend, realize the input material. The presentation of material in typical situations of communication allows for display. The teacher either creates situations himself or uses visual aids (pictures, objects, etc.), accompanying the demonstration with statements and some explanations, observing the reaction of students. Since familiarization with educational material is of great importance for assimilation, according to psychologists, it must be organized in such a way as to affect the emotional sphere of students, their thinking.

Thus, it should be noted that in order to use oral speech effectively as the means of teaching a foreign language, attention should be paid to the implementation of the following factors: the teacher must be fluent in the language being taught and adapt his oral speech to the specific conditions of the audience, without violating the authenticity of speech; be creative when using standard learning technologies; maintain a high level of foreign language proficiency through constant language studies, by reading original literature, listening to audio materials and watching

original video materials in foreign languages. In addition, the teacher must know the capabilities of each student individually for the choice of methodological techniques, as well as the use of real situations. To improve the quality of education, it is necessary to pay attention to additional visual aids that serve to facilitate the assimilation of educational material, as well as to ensure a sufficiently high level of employment.

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